

Indian Farm Bill 2020 and Current Indian Agriculture

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SUMMARY

According to Kushal Pal Singh “Land is an emotional subject with a farmer in India because it is his only means of income”. Farmer is directly or indirectly considered as a father figure because; he grows food for the entire population in the world. Current situation for farmers is not good, as farmer produces his own goods but he is not getting good price for his produce, and there is no any government rules and regulations. Recently Indian government implement three acts viz., The Farmers' Produce Trade and Commerce (Promotion and Facilitation) Act, The Essential Commodities (Amendment) Act and The Farmers (Empowerment and Protection) Agreement on Price Assurance and Farm Services Act for better growth and income of farmer and agriculture. This policy is implemented throughout the India.

INTRODUCTION

Currently Indian government has passed three acts in assembly for protection of farmer and development of farmers life and to sell their harvested crops outside the place where it grown. The notified Agricultural Produce Market Committee (APMC) mandates without paying any state taxes or fees, cess. Farmers are having rights and freedom of choice to sale and purchase the farmers' produce. Crops which facilitates remunerative any prices through Agriculture Market competitive alternative any trading with undue broker commissions, APMC market fees, and monopoly Competition of associations damaging the agricultural Crop. Farmer means an individual engaged in the production of farmers' produce by self or by hired labor or otherwise, and includes the farmer producer organization; Central government three act are passed in assembly 2020 for better benefit and growth of farmer for Development farmer life

1. Farmers' Produce Trade and Commerce (Promotion and Facilitation) Act, 2020

Key Points farm act wise

1. Farmer scope increase in any trade areas this depends any place collection aggregation and production
2. Electronic System and E- Commerce Producer farmer allows
3. Prohibited State government Any Market Fee, Tax And Cess levy on farmers, traders, and electronic trading platforms for the trade of farmers' produce conducted in an 'outside trade area
4. Farmer allows intra-state Trade and inter-state trade of farmers' produce Commodities beyond the physical premises of APMC markets.
5. Any stock limit on agricultural produce must be based on price rise. A stock limit may be imposed only if there is: (i) a 100% increase in retail price of horticultural produce; and (ii) a 50% increase in the retail price of non-perishable agricultural food items.
6. Develop a Price Information and Market Intelligence System for farmers' produce and a framework for dissemination of information
7. Trade of farmers' produce: The Ordinance allows intra-state and inter-state trade of farmers' produce outside
8. Electronic trading: The Ordinance permits the electronic trading of scheduled farmers' produce (agricultural produce regulated under any state APMC Act) in the specified trade area

9. Market fee abolished: The Ordinance prohibits state governments from levying any market fee, cess or levy on farmers, traders, and electronic trading platforms for trade of farmers' produce conducted in an 'outside trade area'.

Main provisions/Discussion –

1. The new legislation will create an ecosystem where the farmers and traders will enjoy freedom of choice of sale and purchase of agri-produce.
2. It will also promote barrier-free inter-state and intra-state trade and commerce outside the physical premises of markets notified under State Agricultural Produce Marketing legislations.
3. The farmers will not be charged any cess or levy for sale of their produce and will not have to bear transport costs.
4. The Bill also proposes an electronic trading in transaction platform for ensuring a seamless trade electronically.
5. In addition to mandis, freedom to do trading at farmgate, cold storage, warehouse, processing units etc.
6. Farmers will be able to engage in direct marketing thereby eliminating intermediaries resulting in full realization of price.
7. the Sub-Divisional Magistrate who shall refer such dispute to a Conciliation Board to be appointed by him for facilitating the binding settlement of the dispute

2. The Farmers (Empowerment and Protection) Agreement on Price Assurance and Farm Services Act, 2020

Key point mention in this act

1. Farmer agreement and its periods: - 1. Written farming agreement
2. The minimum period of the farming agreement shall be for one crop season or one production cycle of livestock to maximum 5 years
3. Farming agreement may identify and require as a condition for the performance of such agreement compliance with mutually acceptable
4. Price is paid is mentioned in agreement
5. Sponsor prohibited from acquiring ownership rights or making permanent modifications on farmer's land or premises.
6. Linkage of farming agreement with insurance or credit.
7. Every farming agreement shall explicitly provide for a conciliation process and formation of a conciliation board consisting of representatives of parties to the agreement
8. Act not to apply to stock exchanges and clearing corporations.

Main Provision Discussion -

1. The Farmers (Empowerment and Protection) Agreement on Price Assurance
2. Farming agreement
3. The agreement may provide for mutually agreed terms and conditions for
4. Duration of agreement
5. Exemptions from existing laws
6. Pricing of farming product
7. Timely acceptance of deliveries of Commodities and will take deliveries within the formation agreed time.
8. Dispute Settlement Mechanism

Benefits

1. Under new law provision
2. Price Assurance to farmer before sowing any crop minimum and maximum price.
3. Price Risk of market situation unpredictable transfer of farmer to purchase sponsor
4. Modern agriculture technology Used For all activities of crop
5. It will also enable the farmer to access modern technology, better seed and other inputs.
6. It will benefit income of farmer increase and reduce Cost of All activities of marketing
7. Any dispute resolution any farmer related has been provided for with clear time baselines for redressal.

3. Essential Commodities (Amendment) Act, 2020**Key Points mention in this act**

1. Removes foodstuff such as cereals, pulses, potato, onions, edible oilseeds, and oils, from the list of essential commodities, removing stockholding limits on agricultural items produced by Horticulture techniques except under "extraordinary circumstances"
2. Requires that imposition of any stock limit on agricultural produce only occur if there is a steep price rise
3. The Essential Commodities (Amendment) Ordinance, 2020
4. Regulation of food items: The Essential Commodities Act, 1955 under regulation add
5. Stock limit: The Ordinance requires that imposition of any stock limit on agricultural produce must be based on price rise.

Main Provision/ Discussion -

1. Central Government Are mention some commodities such as food items, fertilizers, and petroleum products) as essential commodities
2. Any action on imposing stock limit shall be based on price rise and an order for regulating stock limit of any agricultural produce
 - a. Hundred per cent. increase in the retail price of horticultural produce; or
 - b. Fifty per cent. increase in the retail price of non-perishable agricultural foodstuffs, over the price prevailing immediately preceding twelve months, or average retail price of last five years, whichever is lower:

CONCLUSION

To conclude, Farmer is a backbone of Agriculture sector and Agriculture is soul of nation. Hence an Indian farmer bill 2020 is helpful to increase farmer income and better life. Price is not constant for agricultural product but good price assurance in market is assured by the government to farmers in APMCs Market. According to this act farmer has given the full freedom to sell their product to anyone in the country.

REFERENCES

The Farmers' Produce Trade and Commerce (Promotion and Facilitation) Bill, 2020 pdf

Farmers (Empowerment and Protection) Agreement on Price Assurance and Farm Services Act, 2020

Essential Commodities (Amendment) Act, 2020

<https://legislative.gov.in/constitution-of-india>